

INDUSTRY-ORIENTED ASSESSMENT OF THE FATIGUE LIFE OF THIN-WALLED PROFILE WELDMENTS USED IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF BUS BODIES

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The paper presents findings from the intensive cooperation of the university research center with manufacturers of buses, trolleybuses, and electric buses in solving commercial projects, which are aimed, among other things, at solving the strength and fatigue life of their bodywork. The successive steps of the methodology are the creation of the MBS model of the vehicle and the simulation of its driving over an artificial standardised obstacle. The FEM model of the body is loaded with the calculated forces acting in the suspension elements (shock absorbers and air springs) and the stress responses on the critical structural nodes are calculated. Then, the S-N curves of these structural nodes are estimated or, even better, determined experimentally, and the future service stress spectra for the vehicle's design life are estimated. Using the fatigue damage accumulation hypothesis, the permissible maximum stress amplitude in the design spectrum can be determined and compared with the calculated or measured value. A case study from practice concretely documents the procedure.

Keywords: Bus bodywork, Welded bodywork nodes, Damage accumulation, Fatigue life prediction

METHODOLOGY

VZU Plzeň, the Research and Testing Institute Pilsen, has been practicing its methodology for designing, dimensioning and testing bus bodyworks for decades. It was successfully used for the development of several Skoda trolleybuses and buses. This success is evidenced by these vehicles developing virtually no or rare fatigue cracks in service.

The methodology is now being further developed at the Regional Technological Institute, the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering research center at the University of West Bohemia in Pilsen, and other bus manufacturers. It was presented several times in professional literature by Kepka and Rehor [1] and recently by Kepka and Kepka Jr. [2]. Over the years, several milestones have influenced the methodology, Figure 1, the main ones being:

- Participation of the authors in the solution of the European Commission project: Bus-Expert-System for Dynamics Simulation, Design, and Quality Control, Grant agreement ID: CP94-520;
- Implementation of design stress spectra according to Heuler and Klätschke [3];
- Introduction of a simplified probabilistic approach to interpreting fatigue life according to Kliman et al. [4].

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FIGURE 1 History of methodology and its milestones.

FIGURE 2 Calculation part of the methodology.

Once the fundamental structural characteristics of the vehicle are identified, the engineers develop relevant computational models (MBS and FEM). The purpose of multibody simulations of vehicles is to calculate time histories and frequency profiles of kinematic and dynamic quantities which reflect the dynamic properties of the vehicle. It has been confirmed that the main factors in a city vehicle's fatigue life are its vertical dynamic characteristics and the stress response of critical structural details of the bodywork to a ride across an uneven road surface. The effects of considerable road surface irregularities can be simulated effectively by driving the vehicle across an exactly defined irregularity. An artificial obstacle in the form of a cylinder section with a base of 500 mm and 60 mm height has proven appropriate for this purpose. Dynamic simulations yield force-time plots for the axle suspension, guide rods and other vehicle elements while driving across various arrangements of such artificial obstacles, Polach et al. [5]. The data from such dynamic multibody simulations are input into forced oscillation and stress response calculations using the FE model of the bodywork.

Bus bodyworks are welded from thin-walled (typically closed) steel or aluminium alloy sections. Generally, the fatigue strength of welded structural details can be assessed using three basic approaches: nominal, hot-spot and local. An effective tool for analysing a complex structure, such as a bus bodywork, is a computational mesh for nominal stress analysis. From the vehicle's dynamic response crossing an artificial obstacle, one can derive the maximum amplitude of nominal stresses on critical cross sections through the bodywork, Hejman [6].

Using information on the maximum stress amplitude, one can generate design stress spectra, i.e. histograms of harmonic cycles representing the desired service life of the vehicle bodywork in terms of mileage. The total number of cycles and cycles with the maximum stress amplitude can be obtained by qualified estimates, as can the coefficient of the load spectrum shape, Kepka and Kepka Jr. [7].

Fatigue properties of bodywork structural details of interest can also be estimated at the design stage. That being said, it is much more desirable to use data from statistical evaluation of laboratory-based fatigue tests, which can usually be carried out in advance. With systematic testing, one can gradually populate a database of S-N curves for typical structural details used by the particular manufacturer in the vehicle bodyworks, Kepka et al. [8].

When designing stress spectra for critical structural details of the bodywork, which are available along with relevant S-N curves, one can calculate the fatigue damage and predict the service fatigue life of the bodywork. An appropriate cumulative fatigue damage hypothesis must be applied, Schütz [9]. By considering the scatter of fatigue properties of the structural details, one can predict the fatigue life distribution function and obtain a preliminary assessment of the service reliability of the bodywork even at the design stage.

CASE STUDY

Some parts of the methodology described above are demonstrated on data from developing the ŠKODA articulated trolleybus intended for San Francisco. Although this is an older business order, nothing changes to the validity of the process. The data used are modified for the current public presentation.

The MBS trolleybus model was first created to research this vehicle's dynamic properties and to determine the time histories of exciting forces acting in the air springs and the hydraulic shock absorbers. The trolleybus MBS model with the simplified kinematics of axles' suspension and the

MBS model with the detailed kinematics of axles' suspension were created for both empty and full vehicles, see Figure 2.

FIGURE 3 Visualization of the MBS model of the articulated trolleybus.

Simulating driving manoeuvres (i.e., lane-change manoeuvre according to the standard ISO 3888-1, etc.), driving operations (i.e., braking, acceleration, etc.), and running over a large road unevenness with MBS models is possible. The simulations aim to calculate time histories or FFT results of time histories of kinematic and dynamic quantities during the chosen operational situation.

Running over a large road, unevenness was simulated with the MBS models of empty and full trolleybuses. An artificial test track is created on a common bitumen road with a set of four portable standard bumps (obstacles) spaced out on the smooth road surface 20 meters, the shape of which is defined in the ČSN 30 0560 Czech Standard (Obstacle II: $h = 60$ mm, $d = 500$ mm – see Fig. 3). The first obstacle is run over only with right wheels, the second one with both and the third one only with left wheels at vehicle speed about 40 km/h. The simulation results, the forces acting in the trolleybus suspension elements (i.e., time histories of forces acting in air springs and hydraulic shock absorbers) were used as input data for the calculations of the stresses of the FEM model of the trolleybus bodywork.

The FEM model was created from beam and shell elements. Dynamic calculations were performed in the usual way. First, the modes of 40 natural frequencies were calculated. Subsequently, calculations of the forced vibration of the structure were performed. The exciting forces were taken from the MBS model.

The stress calculations were performed on selected time intervals. The results were processed for beam elements of the FEM model with the help of supporting software written in the Delphi programming language. Time series of stress components from axial forces and moments were searched for each element, i.e. for its nodes. The final time histories of the nominal stresses at specified profile points were compiled from them.

As mentioned, the trolleybus MBS model was driven on an uneven test track. Most often, the highest stress responses in the bodywork were calculated by simulating the passage of obstacles on the middle axle, both wheels simultaneously. Figure 4 shows the result of such calculation analysis for one of the most stressed structural nodes of the bodywork under investigation. It is a welded

structural node in the corner of the door space. Maximum stress amplitude $\sigma_{a,max} = 95$ MPa (nominal stress at point C).

FIGURE 4 Scheme of evaluation of nominal stresses in critical cross-section of a structural node.

Furthermore, it was necessary to assess what constructional and material solution of this structural node would satisfy the requirement for the service fatigue life with sufficient reliability. The stress on the bodywork in real operation has the character of random loading processes. The corresponding stress spectra must be estimated at the design stage of the bodywork.

The design stress spectra for this parametric study were generated using the relative coordinates $\sigma_{ai} / \sigma_{a,max}$:

$$h_i = H_{tot} \cdot \left(\frac{H_{max}}{H_{tot}} \right) \left(\frac{\sigma_{ai}}{\sigma_{a,max}} \right)^s \quad (1)$$

Therefore, the design stress spectrum parameters ($s, H_{tot}, \sigma_{a,max},$ and H_{max}) for designing and sizing the beam joints of the bodywork were selected based on the following considerations. The major cause of the service loads that act on the structural detail is the vibration of the bodywork due to the vehicle's ride on irregular road surfaces of various qualities. For this reason, the shape parameter of the design stress spectrum was chosen as $s = 1$.

The design life of the trolleybus bodywork was set as $L_d = 500,000$ km. The dominant vibration frequency was assumed to be 10 Hz. The average travel speed was set as 50 kph. The total number of cycles in the specified bodywork life was estimated as $H_{tot} = 3,6 \cdot 10^8$ cycles. The occurrence of a cycle with maximum stress amplitude H_{max} was considered once per 100 km, that is, $H_{max} = 5 \cdot 10^3$ cycles.

The durability of a material or a component against high cycle fatigue damage is usually characterised by an S-N curve, which describes a relationship between stress amplitude σ_a (or stress range $\Delta\sigma$) and cycles to fatigue failure N_f (or occurrence of a macroscopic fatigue crack). Some standards, for example, BS 7608:1993-Fatigue design and assessment of steel structures, are suitable for considering the scatter of material properties (or fatigue characteristics of assessed construction nodes). In this standard, the fatigue curve is defined as follows:

$$\log(N_f) = \log C_0 - s \cdot d - m \cdot \log(\sigma_a) \quad (2)$$

Laboratory fatigue testing was carried out to determine the fatigue strength of the evaluated structural detail. Figure 5 shows a photograph of the test stand.

The critical cross-section of tested welded nodes was subjected to reverse bending load (the cycle stress ratio was $R = -1$). The limit state was defined by the instant a macroscopic fatigue crack form (1 to 2 mm). In all cases, fatigue cracks initiated in the transition zone of the fillet weld.

The structural nodes with and without reinforcement were tested, and two materials were considered in this study (low-carbon steel and stainless steel). Statistical evaluation of the fatigue test data yielded the parameters of the S-N curve in the form Eq. (2), see schematic pictures of nodes A, B and C in Fig. 6.

FIGURE 5 Laboratory fatigue test of bodywork structural node.

FIGURE 6 Bodywork structural nodes and S-N curves.

The fatigue damage D is calculated using a linear cumulative damage rule, Figure 7.

FIGURE 7 Boundary conditions for calculating cumulative fatigue damage:
a - Palmgren-Miner original, b - Palmgren-Miner elementary, c – Haibach, d - Liu-Zenner.

According to this rule, the limit state concerning fatigue is reached (i.e., the fatigue life of the structural part is exhausted) when the following condition is met:

$$D = \sum_i \frac{n_i}{N_i} = D_{lim} \tag{3}$$

In the present case, the Haibach-modified version of the Palmgren-Miner rule was chosen for calculating fatigue damage.

The limit number of cycles N_i was determined as follows:

- for $\sigma_{ai} \geq \sigma_c$:
$$N_i = N_c \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_{ai}}\right)^w \tag{4}$$

- for $\sigma_c > \sigma_{ai} \geq \sigma_{ath}$:
$$N_i = N_c \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_{ai}}\right)^{w_d} \tag{5}$$

Haibach [10] recommends that the exponent for the lower part of the S-N curve be set as $w_d = 2 \cdot w - 1$. The threshold stress amplitude for taking the resulting fatigue damage into account was given as $\sigma_{ath} = 0.5 \cdot \sigma_c$ in the present case. To safely provide for calculation inaccuracy associated with the use of the cumulative fatigue damage rule, the limit value of fatigue damage was taken as $D_{lim} = 0.5$.

Based on the desired service life, S-N curve parameters, and a design stress spectrum, the maximum permissible service stress levels ($\sigma_{a,max,p}$) for a particular cross-section of a component or structural detail can be determined. This procedure is outlined in Figure 8.

FIGURE 8 Schematic representation of the procedure for finding a design stress spectrum's maximum permissible stress amplitude.

RESULTS

The final results of this case study are shown in Fig. 9, 10 and 11. The structural node A does not absolutely meet the required service life. Even the structural node B does not achieve the required service fatigue life with sufficient reliability. Only the structural node C could be recommended

because it meets the required service fatigue life with the usual design reliability (survival probability higher than 97.7%).

FIGURE 9 Maximum calculated stress amplitude (black) and permissible values – node A.

FIGURE 10 Maximum calculated stress amplitude (black) and permissible values – node B.

FIGURE 11 Maximum calculated stress amplitude (black) and permissible values – node C.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

$\sigma_{a,max}$	- maximum stress amplitude in the spectrum
H_{max}	- number of cycles with $\sigma_{a,max}$ amplitude
H_{tot}	- total number of cycles in the spectrum
s	- shape parameter of the spectrum
h_i	- cumulative frequency of cycles with σ_{ai} amplitude
N_f	- number of cycles to limit fatigue stage
σ_a	- stress amplitude
m	- inverse slope of the σ_a versus $\log N_f$
s	- standard deviation of $\log N_f$
d	- number of standard deviations s below the mean S-N curve
C_0	- parameter defining the mean line S-N relationship
D	- fatigue damage

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